

Analysis of instantaneous choices made by the player in a game based on his/her behavioral character

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Abstract¹— The present study was conducted to identify the behavior of video game players before and during the game. In this regard, a maze computer game was designed. 20 players from Tabriz University of Islamic Arts participated in this study. Before the game, the players demonstrated their behavioral personality by answering 30 questions based on Bartle's theory. Then, by playing the game and making their choices during the game, their behavioral personality was re-examined. Based on the findings of this study, a significant percentage of participants showed a killer personality. But during the game and faced with a momentary choice in the game, even other participants who did not demonstrate a killer personality in the questionnaire also showed the behavior of a killer. According to the obtained results and their analysis, there is a desire to compete and win, which is one of the main personality traits of killers in most players. Being in a predetermined position in the game scenario can lead to this behavioral character. Based on this finding, it can be concluded that examining players during a game will show more realistic results than personality tests.

Keywords— *Computer games, Instantaneous behaviour, Instantaneous choice, Behavioural character, Game theory*

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, compared to other types of media, computer games have a greater impact and feedback in the ordinary culture of the people, and the speed of entry and integration of games into people's lives can be exemplified by the variety of games over time [1]. According to the ESA report in 2015, the gaming industry sold over \$ 22 billion last year (2014), with nearly 63 million Americans playing an average of three hours a week [2]. Despite this source of entertainment being available to many users, the challenge of generating revenue and profitability for game companies has always existed. Although the game development team has always

tried to build a game to interest players in any age group, gender or nationality, only about 10% of the games offered are profitable and only half of them have sold over 10,000 copies [3].

Research on computer games and their effects is a new topic. Research findings on computer games have been combined with a variety of different aspects of its effectiveness. In addition to the great emphasis on studies and research on the positive aspects of video games, there has always been a discussion of the negative aspects of computer games on players [4].

Until now, many positive cognitive effects have been reported by video games. In other words, these games have the ability to improve various aspects of a person's cognitive function. Aspects such as Visual Sensitivity, Task Switching, Spatial Cognition or even Attention [5].

II. RESEARCH BACKGROUND

In 1996, Bartle first examined and categorized video game players in multiplayer games. Success seekers, explorers, socialists, and fighters or Assassins. This taxonomy by Bartle is in fact the main framework for the classification of players. Bartle's theory was a prelude to other theorists expanding this category and adding and defining other categories of players, inspired by the original taxonomy provided by Bartle[6][7][8].

Inspired by the core framework of Bartel's theory, Andre Markzowski divides players into six categories: Disruptor, Philanthropist, Free Spirit, Socializer, Achiever, and Player. Markzowski's model is important because it can be implemented not only in games, but also in the workplace[9]. Nicole McMahon, Peta Wyeth, and Daniel Johnson conducted a study on Fall-out players, examining their player types and behavioral personalities. The study was based on the Big Five psychological test, and players were divided into four categories based on the personality traits of

¹ This paper is extracted from the MA thesis of the first author Shahriar Derhami.

conscientiousness in the test: Conqueror, Manager, Wanderer and Participant[10][11].

Other studies in this field include Hamari and Tonanen's work. In this study, the five main personality traits related to players' motivation, desire and thinking direction are classified as follows: Achievement, Exploration, Sociability, Domination and Immersion[12].

Although these studies were based on Bartle's original theory, they actually show that Bartle's four defining characters for players can be interpreted as the players' personality titles, and in fact more categories for player taxonomy in taken over[13][14].

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The present research method is quasi-experimental (field experiments and surveys) and the information obtained has been analyzed and classified through playing games and interviews by the statistical population.

A. Participants

The statistical population of this study included 20 male and female students of Tabriz University of Islamic Arts, Faculty of Multimedia in the academic year 2020-2021.

B. Sampling Method

The sampling method used in this study was convenience sampling.

C. Data Collection tools

Research data collection tools included two categories:

1- A standard questionnaire, including 30 this or that questions, is designed based on the Bartle's behavioral questionnaire and videos game players are asked to answer them before the game starts.

2- Data extracted from the selection of players in 2 stages and during the game.

D. Data collection Methods

At first, the research statistical population was asked to answer a 30-item questionnaire. The participants were then invited to play the game and information related to their choice in the game was collected.

E. Data analysis

To confirm the reliability of the questions, the Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated and using the obtained value, a significant relationship between the participants' gender and the selection of the assassin group was proved.

Then, the momentary selection of the player during the game was analyzed and the obvious change of the player's behavior to another character category was shown during the game.

F. The Designed Game

The design of this game is inspired by one of the well-known game styles, The Maze Runner. This game challenges the

player along the path of a maze by engaging the player's location recognition as well as his reaction speed along with guessing and predicting the path in front of him. The proper complexity in designing the maze route, in addition to making this match attractive to the player, creates a sense of curiosity and enthusiasm in the player to finish the game.

While the designed game is 2D, at the beginning player has the ability to check the surroundings and movement controls in a 3D space. It is optional for him/her to change and modify the controller for his/her desire.

Fig.1. The view of the game. Player icon shows as a red indicator

G. Game scenario and implementation

The game scenario is defined in such a way that 2 players will start playing on 2 different personal computers separately but at the same time. The maze route begins to become clear with the movement of the player's cursor in a certain radius. Coins are placed along the path and inside the maze so that the player can gain points by collecting them. There are 6 coins and each coin has 100 points.

When the total points reach 300, a box will appear including 4 choices for the player. The player will have the right to choose from the options for a limited time. The same box will be displayed to the player when the points are accumulated and 600 points are reached. These 4 options include:

- Increase my time
- Hide my blur
- Decrease opponent timer
- Change opponent map

Fig.2. 4 options appear for player in time of reaching 300 and 600 points

IV. FINDINGS

The number of players participating in this study was 20, which are demonstrated in Table 1.

TABLE I Demographic characteristics of the participants

Gender		Education		Age
Male	Female	Bachelor	Masters	Average
10 (50%)	10 (50%)	0	20 (100%)	24.7

By observing the results of a 30-item questionnaire that was completed by each of the 20 players before the game, the following average personality classification (Figure 3) was obtained.

Fig.3. Categorization of player personality among participants

To evaluate the questionnaire and calculate the Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 30 questions in the answer sheet, the value of 0.774 was calculated using SPSS software, which indicates the reliability of the questions in this questionnaire (Figure 4).

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	20	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	20	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.744	30

Fig.4. - Cronbach's alpha value of the questionnaire

According to the scenario set for the game, players will have the right to choose between 4 options during the game in 2 rounds according to the points earned as a bonus.

These 4 options focus on 3 personality categories of success seekers, explorers and assassins, and the result of this choice

during the game among players shows a significant increase in the selection of options related to the assassin category among the participants. So that 15 people absolutely choose the options related to the assassin category and 3 people had one of their two choices to be in the "assassins" category. In the meantime, only 1 person had choices in the success seekers category, and 1 person showed the success seeker behavior in the first place and the explorer behavior in the next choice.

V. CONCLUSION

By observing the questionnaire results and also the choices of players, apart from the effect of gender on players in the "assassins" category, the momentary choice of players also shows the desire to reflect the behavior of this group among participants. The gender factor in the "success seekers" category also shows a significant relationship between participants. But in the other two categories of players, the gender factor has no effect on the choice and rejects this hypothesis.

According to the information obtained from the participants, during playing and in the moment of choice, the desire to show the "assassins" behavioral character is clearly visible. These data indicate the existence of a killer behavioral personality among the participants, despite what they answered in the questionnaire, and can indicate that by being in the gameplay position, the player uses his sense of competition and superiority to achieve the goal and victory, and this behavioral character is revealed.

VI. SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS OF RESEARCH

Due to the need for research or in other words, marketing before creating videos games and also designing the game scenario, such research can greatly determine the market in front of the game as well as its audience. Planning and setting the main goal in the game scenario, depending on what category or character group the target players are in, will help the development team to estimate the game feedback more accurately.

This information can also be used for in-game sales, and according to these results, lead more selling options and facilities to the target group of players in the game.

VII. LIMITATIONS OF RESEARCH AND SCIENTIFIC WORK

At the time of the test, according to the existing limitations due to the prevalence of Covid-19 disease, the test faced issues in implementation on a statistical basis; issues that led to a more limited number of people participating in this test. Also, providing suitable conditions for the participants, away from the risk of Covid-19 disease, was another limitation in this study. On the other hand, due to time constraints and other factors such as several players playing simultaneously and in larger dimensions, designing an online game with a

more complex scenario to see more behavioral personality of socialist players was not possible.

VII. FUTURE RESEARCH

Providing a wider statistical community will be a factor in obtaining more accurate information on this subject and leads to more comprehensive results. Additional post-game psychological tests can also be used to obtain more accurate information about players' behavior.

If possible, designing a multiplayer and online game that has the ability to support a large number of players can also be implemented to complete information about the socialist personality group. However, various other factors are also involved in showing a player's behavioral personality. Factors such as age, location or even race. This research is performed with the mentioned statistical community only, and cannot fully define the community of players and their behavior during a game.

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